

A Study on Consumer Awareness on Amway Products

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Consumer is the foundation for every business. It is very easy to arrange finance, people, Machines, materials and whatever required for starting a business concern but indeed it is very difficult to attract the consumer towards the business concern. The volume of profit of a business is decided by its potential consumers' strength.

Every business unit always focuses all its efforts in increasing the consumer base. Advertisements, discount offers, Changes in Packages, services to the products, Create the Convenience for the Consumer etc., are the examples of promotional activities to reach the consumer mind so that it can easily increase the sales which result in profit maximization.

This is an attempt to know the consumer awareness about Amway Products among the college students. The Amway India Enterprises commenced its business operation in the year 1998. This company started its business with five products. Now in 2018, it has more than 130 products. This is a direct selling business. The sales of this business are directly depended on its distributors who first create awareness, promote and sell the products.

Statement of the Problem

Amway is a business which promotes its business through its distributors. It provides knowledge about products, sales and marketing to its distributors those are really willing to build their business with Amway. The distributors would do this for their convenience, desires to earn and either as part time or full time. So their efforts to get knowledge about products, sales and marketing and also apply the knowledge to promote and sell the products are all directly depending on their determination to the income which they want to earn through this business.

It is the policy of this business not to advertise its products like other business. Its promotional techniques are different from other business. The only way to reach its consumers is its distributors. There is no control over distributors because they would do the sales

activities only for their goal and convenience and not for the sake of the Amway Company's goal. We know that advertisement is much needed one for any type of products and services. But this concern is doing its business differently. Here this study is going to analyse the awareness level of respondents about the Amway products and this study aims at to reveal the solution for the following questions: i) How many students are using the Amway products? ii) How many products are used by them and their family ? and iii) How many respondents are not knowing the products?.

Objectives

1. To know the awareness level of respondents about Amway Products.
2. To find the usage level of respondents with regard to Amway products.

Hypothesis

1. Ho : There is no association between awareness and region.
2. Ho: There is no relationship between level of income and level of awareness.

Scope of the Study

This study aims at to know the consumer awareness about the Amway products. Here the researcher considers the students from UG and PG Degree of Bishop Heber College as respondents for this study. As every student is representing a family, the researcher has chosen students as respondents to analyse the consumer awareness about Amway products.

Methodology

Sample Size: The researcher has conducted this study by collecting data from students of one UG and one PG class. The strength of UG and PG students who have given responses is 110. Hence the size of the sample for this study is 110.

Sampling Method: For collecting data from the students, convenience random sampling method was used by the researcher with the help of structured questionnaires. The questionnaires were distributed and data were collected from the one UG class and the one PG class.

Statistical Tools for Analysis: Percentage analysis and Chi-Square Test are used to analyse the collected data and then they are interpreted.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1

Demographical Classification of respondents on the basis of Gender		
Gender	No.of Respondents	%
Male	49	44.55
Female	61	55.45
Total	110	100
On the basis of Educational qualification		
Degree	No.of Respondents	%
UG	65	59.09
PG	45	40.91
Total	110	100
On the basis of Region		
Region	No.of Respondents	%
Rural	41	37.27

Urban	69	62.73
Total	110	100
On the basis of Family Income		
Family Income(Rs)	No.of Respondents	%
Below Rs.15,000	23	20.91
Rs.15,000 – Rs. 30,000	55	50.00
Rs.30,000 – Rs.45,000	19	17.27
Above Rs.45,000	13	11.82
Total	110	100

The above table gives details about demographical data of the respondents. Out of 110 respondents, 44.55% respondents are male and 55.45% are female. Regarding educational qualification of respondents, 59.09% respondents are studying UG degree and 40.91% are belonging to PG degree. According to regional classification of respondents, 62.73% respondents are belonging to Urban area and 37.27 % are belonging to rural area. When the classification is done on the basis of family income, 50% of the respondents are belonging to the income group of Rs.15,000 – Rs.30,000, 11.82% respondents are in the income group of above Rs.45,000.

Table 2

Classification of respondents on the basis of Awareness on Amway Products		
Awareness	No.of Respondents	%
Know	103	93.64
Don't Know	7	6.36
Total	110	100

From the table No.2. it is clearly known that 93.64% respondents aware the Amway and its products. 6.36% don't aware even the Amway, the company name and its products.

Table 3

Classification of respondents on the basis of Level of Awareness on no. of Amway Products		
No.of products	No.of Respondents	%
Below 5	80	77.67
6 - 10	17	16.51
11 - 15	4	3.88
Above 15	2	1.94
Total	103	100

From the above table, It is known that 77.67% respondents know only 5 and below 5 products out of 130 products. It is pathetic to know that only 1.94% respondents know more than 15 products of out of 130 of its products.

Table 4

Classification of Respondents on the basis of usage of Amway products		
Using the Products	No.of Respondents	%
Yes	19	18.45
No	84	81.55
Total	103	100

The Table no.4 Shows that number of respondents are at present using amway products. According to the table, only 18.45% are at present using the amway products and 81.55% are not using the products.

Testing of Hypothesis

1. Testing the Relationship between Region and awareness

It is hypothesised that there is a relationship between region of the respondents and the awareness of the Amway products. This relationship is tested with the help of a chi square test. The Null Hypothesis framed for this purpose is ‘There is no relationship between the Region and the Awareness of Amway Products ‘.

Table 5

Regional Awareness of the Respondents				
Region	No. of Respondents			
	Know	%	Don't know	%
Rural	36	34.95	5	71.43
Urban	67	65.05	2	28.57
Total	103	100	7	100

The calculated value for the observed frequencies provided in Table 5. is 2.5. The table value for 1 degree of freedom at five per cent level of significance is 3.84. A comparison of the calculated value with that of the table value indicates that the calculated value is less than the table value and hence the Null Hypothesis that ‘there is no relationship between the Region and the Awareness of Amway Products ‘ has been accepted.

This provides the conclusion that the awareness of respondents is similar whether they are either in rural or urban.

2. Testing the Relationship between level of Income and level of Awareness.

Another hypothesis is framed for testing the relationship between level of income and level of awareness. The Null Hypothesis is “there is no relationship between the Level of Income and the Level of Awareness of Amway Products”. This is also tested with the help of chi square test.

Table 6

Classification of Respondents on the basis of Level of Income and Level of Awareness					
Level of Income	Below Rs.15,000	Rs.15,000 – Rs.30,000	Rs.30,000 – Rs.45,000	Above Rs.45,000	Total
Level of Awareness					
Below 5	17	48	10	5	80
6 - 10	2	4	7	4	17
11 - 15	-	1	1	2	4
Above 16	-	-	1	1	2
Total	19	53	19	12	103

The calculated value for the observed frequencies provided in Table 6. is 26.28. The table value for 9 degrees of freedom at five per cent level of significance is 16.9. A comparison of the calculated value with that of the table value indicates that the calculated value is greater than the table value and hence the Null Hypothesis that ‘there is no relationship between the Level of Income and the Level of Awareness of Amway Products ‘ has been rejected. Hence there is a relationship between the Level of Income and the Level of Awareness of Amway Products. This provides the conclusion that the level of awareness of respondents is influenced by the level of income of the respondents.

Findings

- From the above analysis, the following findings are extracted and listed here:
- Out of 110 respondents, 44.55% respondents are male and 55.45% are female.
- Regarding educational qualification of respondents, 59.09% respondents are studying UG degree and 40.91% are belonging to PG degree.
- According to regional classification of respondents, 62.73% respondents are belonging to urban area and 37.27 % are belonging to rural area.
- When the classification is done on the basis of family income, 50% of the respondents are belonging to the income group of Rs.15,000 – Rs.30,000, 11.82% respondents are in the income group of Above Rs.45,000. 20.91% respondents are in the income group of Below Rs.15, 000.
- From the table No.2, it is clearly known that 93.64% respondents aware the Amway and its products. 6.36% don’t even aware the Amway, the company name and its products.
- From the table No.3, it is known that 77.67% respondents know only 5 and below 5 products out of 130 products. It is pathetic to notice that only 1.94% respondents know more than 15 products out of 130 of its products.
- It is understood from the Table no.4 that only 18.45% are at present using the Amway products and 81.55% are not using the products.
- It is found from the chi square test analysis of the data given in the table No.5, there is no relationship between region of the respondents and their awareness on Amway products. Hence awareness of the respondents is similar irrespective of their residential area.
- It is also observed from the table No. 6 and its chi square test analysis, there is a significant relationship between level of income and level of awareness of the respondents. Thus the level of family income influences the level of awareness of the respondents on the Amway products.

Suggestions

From the findings of the study, it can be observed that there is a large gap between awareness and usage of Amway products and the level of awareness is also very poor. Hence the company must do something to improve the quantum of awareness of consumers.

Regarding usage of Amway products, the Amway Company needs to evolve a proper strategy to make use of Amway products by the consumers those who only aware the products but not using the products.

Conclusion

This study aims at to know the consumer awareness on the Amway Products with special reference to college students. Consumer awareness is the fundamental for any manufacturer to market his products in the target market. In an information Technology era, it is not hard to create awareness about any products and services but it is really hard to convert the awareness into sales volume. The conversion involves a lot that make real challenge to the marketing manager. Here the Amway Company is facing the challenge because it has a good awareness from the consumers about the company and only for a few products, not for the whole products and apparently the usage of Amway products by the consumers is also proportionate to the few products. Though the Amway Company has unique promotion policy regarding advertisement and trust the distributors for creating awareness and sales, these are not enough to create awareness for the whole products. When the awareness of whole products is not there in the market, obviously the sales of all products are not evenly happened. Hence the Amway Company evolves proper strategies to make the whole products familiar among the consumers thereby sales of all the products are possible.

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